

How PR Influences Consumer Decision-Making: The Psychology of Micro-Moments

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Abstract

The article examines how digitalization and economic uncertainty redefine consumer behavior and clarifies the role of PR communications in shaping decisions within the logic of micro-moments. The aim of the study is to develop and theoretically substantiate a model of the psychological influence of strategic PR tools on the consumer at key points of the digital journey. The methodological basis includes a systematic review of academic sources and a qualitative synthesis of industry reports and practical cases. The findings indicate that the classical funnel has lost explanatory power, giving way to a discrete, fragmented path composed of high-intent micro-moments in which the consumer expects not advertising but vetted information. Under these conditions, PR as a mechanism of earned media serves as a central driver of trust, compensating for the credibility gap characteristic of paid advertising. Case analysis demonstrates that PR strategies oriented toward producing expert content for I-want-to-know moments directly correlate with the generation of qualified leads and growth in organic traffic. It is concluded that integrating PR into a digital marketing strategy is not merely a tool for increasing awareness but a critically important foundation for building long-term relationships with the consumer and achieving measurable business outcomes. The study is addressed to marketing strategists, PR practitioners, and brand managers.

Keywords: *public relations, PR, consumer psychology, micro-moments, decision-making, digital marketing, reputation management, earned media, cognitive biases, brand trust.*

JEL Classification codes: *D83, M31, M37, M30, M14.*

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Introduction

The modern consumer environment is undergoing a structural shift driven by the synergy of two forces: prolonged macroeconomic uncertainty and the total digitalization of choice trajectories. Empirical observations by analysts confirm the scale of change. According to Gartner, by the third quarter of 2025 the share of buyers postponing major purchases will reach 60% versus 28% in 2024, indicating rising caution and heightened price sensitivity (Martech Edge, 2025). Congruent conclusions are shown by Deloitte's analysis: the depletion of pandemic-era savings will restrain consumer activity in 2024–2025 (Deloitte, 2024).

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In parallel with greater spending caution, the very logic of choice is changing. Digital environments are becoming the central hub of the consumer journey: over 80% of people research brands in social media, and almost 70% have already made purchases directly within these channels (McKinsey & Company, 2025). The linear behavioral model is giving way to a fragmented route consisting of numerous brief yet decisive touchpoints — micromoments (Rare Bird, Inc., n.d.; The Story, n.d.). These episodes, structured by intentions (to know, to do, to find, to buy), are turning into key fields of competition for attention and loyalty.

The problem lies in the degradation of the effectiveness of classical marketing instruments focused on interruption and direct persuasion, under conditions of an informed and autonomous audience. Having instant access to sources, consumers deliberately seek not advertising claims but credible, relevant answers to current queries. This yields a research gap: despite developed bodies of work on consumer psychology in digital environments and on the strategic evolution of PR, there is no integral theoretical framework that systematically explains the psychological mechanisms of the influence of strategic PR on the formation of preferences precisely in high-intent micromoments (PR) (Patel & Chauhan, 2024; Torossian, n.d.).

The aim of the study is to analyze and formalize the psychological effects of strategic PR communications on consumer decision-making in the context of digital micromoments.

Scientific novelty lies in the conceptual coupling of consumer psychology theories, the micromoments paradigm, and current PR strategies, culminating in a model in which PR serves as a fundamental mechanism for overcoming the credibility gap in the digital era.

The author's hypothesis is that PR approaches aimed at providing verifiable and valuable information through earned media in micromoments of the I-want-to-know type psychologically outperform paid advertising in building long-term trust and brand preference, since paid messages at the early stages of the journey more often encounter skepticism.

Materials and Methods

The methodological foundation of the study is interdisciplinary and rests on two complementary components: a systematic review of current scientific literature and a qualitative synthesis of authoritative industry reports together with practical cases. This linkage makes it possible not only to consolidate theoretical developments but also to test them against empirical material and in the context of real business practices.

The systematic review covered peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings indexed in Scopus and Web of Science. The search was conducted using the key queries consumer psychology, decision-making in the digital environment, micromoments, public relations, brand trust, and earned media. This approach made it possible to examine the basic concepts that determine consumer behavior online and to trace the transformation of the role of PR in the digital communication space.

Analytical industry reports — publications by leading consulting companies, including Gartner and Deloitte — provided macro-level benchmarks on current and anticipated trends, consumer expectations, and economic sentiment.

Taken together, the methodology ensures a comprehensive examination of the subject matter, combining the analytical depth of academic sources with the applied value of industry analytics and empirical experience, which allows for the formulation of well-grounded and operationalizable conclusions.

Results and Discussion

Decision-making in the digital environment only rarely relies on strictly rational computation; far more often it is determined by the operation of cognitive biases and heuristics — mental shortcuts through which the brain reduces the complexity of choice (Frederiks et al., 2015). Digital platforms are not merely a neutral container for these processes: their interfaces and algorithmic contours deliberately resonate with the aforementioned predispositions and amplify them.

One of the key drivers is the mechanism of social proof. Under conditions of chronic information overload, individuals seek to validate their own preferences by observing the behavior of others. Instruments of the networked environment — reviews, aggregated ratings, like counters, and user-generated content — produce salient signals that calibrate perceptions of quality and levels of trust (Latief et al., 2024). At the same time, instantaneous access to the opinions of similar others diminishes the salience of official brand communications.

Alongside this, the anchoring effect and the strategy of artificial scarcity are widely employed, especially in e-commerce. Displaying the old price next to a promotional price sets an anchor, visually increasing the attractiveness of the discount, whereas notifications such as only 3 units left in stock or the offer expires in... appeal to FOMO and provoke impulsive behavior (Kabir et al., 2025).

The paradox of abundance in digital assortments lies in the fact that expanding choice often induces decision fatigue: when confronted with an excessive number of alternatives, the consumer experiences cognitive overload and regresses to the simplest heuristics — selecting the most popular option, gravitating toward a recognizable brand, or confirming the default option (Frederiks et al., 2015). The systematization of these mechanisms is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Cognitive biases in the digital consumer decision-making process

Bias/Heuristic	Psychological trigger	Digital manifestation	Implication for brands
Social proof	Need for validation, conformity	Reviews, ratings, buyers choice	The necessity of reputation management and incentivizing positive reviews
Anchoring effect	Reliance on the first piece of information received	Was/Now pricing, tariff comparisons	The importance of strategic price presentation to shape perceived value
Scarcity	Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)	Countdown timers, low-stock notifications	Creating a sense of urgency and exclusivity to stimulate immediate action
Confirmation bias	Seeking information that confirms existing beliefs	Personalized feeds and recommendations	Delivering relevant content at early stages to shape the initial opinion
Decision fatigue	Cognitive overload due to choice abundance	Popularity filters, default options	Simplifying choice architecture and highlighting recommended options to reduce cognitive load

Source: compiled by the author based on Latief et al., 2024

Comprehending hidden psychological determinants is the starting point for constructing effective communication strategies. The point is not to attempt to override cognitive biases, but to work in alignment with them: brands achieve more when they transmit precisely those signals and precisely the information that the consumer’s brain instinctively uses to simplify choice.

Further fragmentation of attention under conditions of constant mobile connectivity has destroyed the classical linearity of the consumer journey, turning it into a sequence of discrete, highly

deliberate contacts. These micromoments are brief episodes when a person almost reflexively reaches for a device (primarily a smartphone) to satisfy a suddenly arising need: to learn something, to go somewhere, to perform an action, or to make a purchase (Rare Bird, Inc., n.d.).

In Google analytics such episodes are reduced to four basic types (Pires et al., 2022): moments I-want-to-know (research without readiness for a transaction: for example, the query best running shoes for beginner runners), I-want-to-go (search for a local offer or route: sporting goods stores near me), I-want-to-do (operational assistance: how to choose the right size of running shoes), and I-want-to-buy (a purchase on the home stretch — clarification of the offer or the final check before choosing).

The psychological profile of these episodes is defined by three parameters: urgency (the need must be satisfied here and now), high goal-directedness (the user clearly formulates the query), and contextuality (the query is influenced by place, time, and the current activity). In such moments the expectation bar is maximal: utmost relevance and — especially — speed are required. It has been shown that even a one-second delay in loading a mobile page noticeably reduces conversion (Public Relations Society of America, n.d.; Pires et al., 2022).

The new configuration of behavior renders the classical funnel model inadequate, in which the trajectory — from awareness to purchase — was predictable and managed by the brand. The modern path (see Figure 1) is nonlinear, fragmentary, and in fact orchestrated by the consumer: it consists of numerous micromoments occurring in an arbitrary sequence. The brand’s task is not to push through the funnel, but to be useful in each such episode, when the initiative is taken by the user.

Figure 1. The model of the Consumer Path in Micromoments in Comparison with the Traditional Funnel

Source: compiled by the author based on Rare Bird, Inc., n.d.; Latief et al., 2024; Kabir et al., 2025

In the logic of micro-moments — primarily at the I-want-to-know stage — the consumer expects not an advertising message but a competent, trustworthy answer. As a result, a credibility gap forms between paid communication channels (paid media) and earned media. Because a paid message is by definition tied to the brand’s commercial motivation, it is perceived as biased. In contrast, earned media — materials in reputable publications, reviews by independent experts, mentions by influencers, and feedback from real users — are interpreted as an external, relatively impartial assessment, which substantially increases audience trust.

The economic restraint noted in the introduction only deepens this gap (Martech Edge, 2025; Gartner, n.d.). Under conditions of more cautious consumption, people more intensively seek confirmation of the correctness of their choice from external sources, whereby the authenticity of earned media acquires additional value. Against this backdrop, PR, whose key function is to shape a positive reputation and generate earned mentions, ceases to be an auxiliary tactical tool and becomes a strategic asset that provides trust in a market marked by pronounced skepticism (Shetty & Khadir, 2023; Foxall, 2017).

Empirical indicators demonstrate the superiority of earned and owned media compared to direct advertising in consumer perception, as clearly illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The Level of Consumer Confidence in Various Sources of Information (2024)

Source: compiled by the author based on Commit Agency, n.d.

It is precisely in the I-want-to-know phases that PR tools demonstrate the highest effectiveness. When a user formulates queries such as best solution for... or how to choose..., they are operating in a cognitive rather than a transactional mode. At this moment, direct advertising with a click-through to a product page appears premature and intrusive. In contrast, a link to an in-depth publication in an authoritative industry outlet, an analytical review, or a practical guide prepared within PR activities precisely matches the informational need and positions the brand as an expert and a reliable navigator rather than a seller (Frigenti, 2024). This interaction configuration makes it possible to capture the audience at an early, critically important stage of preference formation and to build a foundation of trust for all subsequent touchpoints.

The transition from theoretical constructs to empirics demonstrates a direct correlation between strategic PR and measurable business metrics. Digital PR, integrated with content marketing and

search engine optimization (SEO), ceases to be a purely image-building tool and transforms into a direct driver of qualified lead acquisition.

Case 1: TRUE (B2B FinTech/sustainability) (The PHA Group, n.d.)

Objective: To initiate a discussion among chief financial officers and sustainability leaders about the return on investment (ROI) of green initiatives.

The core of the campaign was the preparation of two in-depth analytical reports (whitepapers) based on market research. These materials secured for TRUE the status of a thought leader in the niche. The content was featured by leading business and financial media (BBC, Reuters), and the reports themselves served as magnets for collecting contact data of prospective clients. Achieved were over 90 publications in target media, more than 300 report downloads, and an overperformance against the plan for Sales Qualified Leads. This illustrates a coherent funnel: expert PR content → media coverage → lead-magnet download → acquisition of a qualified lead.

Case 2: Celerity (B2B MarTech) (Definition, n.d.).

Objective: To increase the flow of leads for marketing technology services.

PR was defined as the cornerstone of a content-oriented inbound strategy. The tactical focus was obtaining high-quality backlinks from authoritative niche platforms to strengthen the company website's SEO positions. More than 100 new backlinks were obtained, which ensured a 250% increase in organic traffic and formed a sales funnel worth millions of pounds. The example directly links PR activity (link building) with a key digital marketing metric (organic traffic) and the ultimate business effect (revenue).

These cases make it possible to reconstruct the cause-and-effect chain of PR's influence on the consumer journey — from awareness to conversion, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Diagram of the PR Influence on the Path from Awareness to Conversion

Source: compiled by the author based on The PHA Group, n.d.

To move from conceptual findings to practical implementation, they must be operationalized — a clear systematization of tactics and outcome measures. The corresponding structure is presented in Table 2: it is a matrix of key performance indicators (KPI) that links PR activities to specific micro-moments, thereby setting transparent benchmarks for planning, execution, and subsequent evaluation.

Table 2. KPI matrix for PR strategies in micro-moments

Micro-moment	Consumer psychology	Optimal PR tactic	Core KPIs
I-want-to-know	Seeking expertise, reducing uncertainty	Opinion leader articles, whitepapers, research studies	Search engine result positions, referral traffic, quality of backlinks
I-want-to-do	Seeking practical guidance and instructions	Publishing how-to guides and instructional videos	Engagement (time on page, page depth), social shares
I-want-to-buy	Seeking validation and social proof	Publishing reviews, case studies, obtaining awards	Conversion rate from review sites, sentiment analysis of mentions (sentiment analysis)

Source: compiled by the author based on Definition, n.d.; Belle Communication, n.d.; Umukoro, n.d.

In addition to quantitative indicators, qualitative diagnostics are essential. Sentiment analysis makes it possible to capture the direction and intensity with which PR activity shifts brand perception. This metric reflects not only the presence of reach but also its semantic polarity — the balance of positive, neutral, and negative signals. The target ratio to be pursued is visualized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Ideal Distribution of the Tone of Mentions in the PR Campaign

Source: compiled by the author based on Deloitte, 2024; The PHA Group, n.d.

An effective PR strategy in the context of micro-moments is not a race for the number of mentions, but a consistent production of verifiable, substantive content that addresses the audience’s genuine information requests at critical choice points and converts into verifiable business outcomes.

Conclusion

The conducted study demonstrates that the consumer trajectory under digitalization and the current macroeconomic dynamics has undergone a qualitative transformation. It has lost linearity and predictability, turning into a mosaic sequence of psychologically autonomous micro-moments, where a person, guided by a specific intention, seeks to obtain instant and relevant answers.

The key results can be summarized as follows: against the backdrop of increased economic prudence and cognitive overload, the role of trust in decision-making is radically strengthened, generating a credibility gap between paid media and earned channels. Strategic PR communications focused on producing substantive content for earned media prove to be the most effective mechanism for narrowing this gap: the brand enters the information field not as an intrusive seller, but as a competent and trustworthy guide.

The maximum effect of such communication manifests in I-want-to-know micro-moments, when the user is at an early research stage and most open to authoritative sources. Successful interaction at this moment forms the foundation of future loyalty. This confirms the proposed hypothesis: PR strategies based on creating value and accumulating trust psychologically outperform, in their long-term impact, traditional advertising models built on attention interruption.

The practical significance lies in revising the status of PR within the marketing architecture. Functional isolation of PR units and marketing departments becomes unacceptable; to operate effectively within the logic of micro-moments, PR specialists need competencies in SEO, content marketing, and web analytics. The effectiveness of their activities should be evaluated not by the number of publications, but by specific business metrics — traffic quality, the volume and quality of lead generation, and ultimately the contribution to revenue. The presented model and KPI matrix serve as a practical guide for the development and evaluation of integrated communication strategies.

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